

Certification of Forest Management and Ecosystem Services

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Forest management certification is a process that seeks to ensure that forests are managed sustainably, taking into account environmental, social and economic criteria. In Portugal, the main forest certification systems used are the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC®) and the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC). These systems promote practices to ensure the conservation of biodiversity, the protection of soil and water resources, as well as seeking to guarantee fair conditions for local communities and workers. Data as of January 2025 points to 649,350 hectares in Portugal. The forest management certification process was originated in a worldwide civic movement that began in the 1990s, motivated by the need to protect tropical forests from the advance of timber companies, and which gradually spread to all the world's forests. This movement reflects the growing environmental awareness of society valuing wood and other sustainably produced forest products, which is translated into added economic value for the forest products and therefore increasing profitability for forest producers and/or owners. Forest certification is a voluntary process that involves several stages and can be carried out individually or as a group. Group forest certification is especially advantageous for smallholders as it allows several properties or forest areas to unite under a single certificate, sharing costs and responsibilities while ensuring compliance with the requirements of the chosen certification system (FSC or PEFC). Certification systems have evolved to recognize the additional benefits provided by forests, beyond the production of goods, known as ecosystem services. In Portugal, the FSC has a system for certifying ecosystem services. Biodiversity as well as the carbon sequestration and storing ecosystem services are recognized. At the beginning of 2025, 8 of the 88 ecosystem service certificates worldwide were Portuguese.

Júlio Germano de Souza(1);
Pedro Gomes(2); Eduardo
Pousa(3); José Castro(3); Marina
Castro(1)

(1) CIMO, LA SusTEC, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

(2) Baladi – Federação Nacional dos Baldios. R. Marshal Teixeira Rebelo 153-121, 5000-651 Vila Real, Portugal

(3) Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

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